

HARMFUL Phytoplankton Species in the Central Colombian Caribbean Oceanic Province

Fig. 1. Sampling sites in the Colombian Central Caribbean Oceanic Province.

Historically, research on phytoplankton and phytobenthos from the Colombian Caribbean Sea has focused on neritic waters. This neritic zone, constitutes less than 6% (30,219 km²) of the total Colombian Caribbean area, whereas the remaining 94% (501,935 km²) remains largely unexplored. A review of the extant literature revealed the presence of 13 harmful microalgal species in coastal waters of the Colombian Caribbean (Table 1).

To ascertain the presence and distribution of harmful microalgae in the oceanic waters of the Colombian Caribbean, the IOC-UNESCO taxonomic reference list of harmful microalgae [1] was used to verify the species reported in a recent investigation, which analysed the phytoplankton composition in 108 samples collected during three expeditions to the Central Colombian Caribbean Oceanic Province (CCOP) [2].

Oceanographic expeditions were conducted during 2015, 2016, and 2017, encompassing a total area of 35,874 km² and 27 stations situated in the vicinity of the Magdalena River, a major waterway in the country (Fig. 1). Water samples were collected using Niskin bottles at 10, 80, and 250 m; vertical tows covering the upper 50 m were conducted using nets with a 20-µm mesh size.

Bottle samples were analysed using the Utermöhl method, and net samples were examined from aliquots (0.125 ml) using accumulation curves. Cells were observed using a Leica Microsystems DMi1 inverted microscope using 20×, 40×, and 63× objectives. Identification was performed to the lowest possible taxonomic level, following various taxonomic keys [3–5]. Using this method, 287 taxa were recorded, and 184 species were identified. A subsequent comparison of taxonomic lists revealed that only 14 species in the CCOP list are considered harmful, of which six are deemed potentially toxic (Table 2). These organisms were identified in the epipelagic zone of the Caribbean Surface Water (CSW), encompassing the upper 10 m, with average temperatures of 28 °C, salinity 36, and dissolved oxygen concentrations of 3.8 mg L⁻¹.

The presence of potentially toxic species such as *Karenia papilionacea* and *Prorocentrum concavum* was also

Table 1. Harmful microalgae species reported in coastal waters of the Colombian Caribbean coast [6–7].

Species	Associated Toxins
<i>Prorocentrum borbonicum</i> L.Ten-Hage, J.Turquet, J.-P.Quod, S.Puiseux-Dao & Couté 2000	Neurotoxic borbotoxins
<i>Prorocentrum cordatum</i> (Ostenfeld) J.D.Dodge 1976	Fast Acting Toxins
<i>Prorocentrum hoffmannianum</i> M.A.Faust 1990	Okadaic acid, Diarrhetic Shellfish Toxins, Fast Acting Toxins
<i>Prorocentrum lima</i> (Ehrenberg) F.Stein 1878	Okadaic acid, DTX-1, DTX-2, prorocontrolide, Diarrhetic Shellfish Toxin, Fast Acting Toxins
<i>Prorocentrum porosum</i> Arteaga-Sogamoso, F.Rodríguez, Amato, Ben-Gigirey, Tibiriçá, Chomerat, Mafra, T.Nishimura, M.Adachi & Mancera-Pineda 2022	Okadaic acid
<i>Prorocentrum rhathymum</i> A.R.Loeblich III, Sherley & R.J.Schmidt 1979	Okadaic acid
<i>Gonyaulax</i> sp. Diesing, 1866	Yessotoxins
<i>Gambierdiscus caribaeus</i> Vandersea, Litaker, M.A.Faust, Kibler, W.C.Holland & P.A.Tester 2009	CTX, IC-CTX analogue, 44-methylgambierone, positive to the Human erythrocyte lysis assay
<i>Ostreopsis cf. ovata</i> Y.Fukuyo 1981	Ovatoxins
<i>Margalefidinium polykrikoides</i> (Margalef) F.Gómez, Richlen & D.M.Anderson 2017	
<i>Anabaena spiroides f. baltica</i> (Johs.Schmidt) Pankow 1965	
<i>Anabaenopsis</i> sp. V.V.Miller, 1923	
<i>Synechocystis</i> sp. Sauvageau, 1892	

Table 2. Harmful microalgae found in the Colombian Central Caribbean Oceanic Province – CCOP.

Type	Species name	Environment and Associated Toxins
Toxic Species	<i>Centrodinium punctatum</i> (Cleve) F.J.R.Taylor 1976	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Saxitoxins, Paralytic Shellfish Toxins
	<i>Dinophysis caudata</i> Kent 1881	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Okadaic acid, DTX1, Diarrhetic Shellfish Toxins
	<i>Dinophysis ovum</i> F.Schütt 1895	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Okadaic acid, Diarrhetic Shellfish Toxins
	<i>Karenia papilionacea</i> A.J.Haywood & K.A.Steidinger 2004	Subtropical Subsurface Water – Epipelagic Zone Brevetoxins
	<i>Phalacroma mitra</i> F.Schütt 1895	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Diarrhetic Shellfish Toxins
	<i>Prorocentrum concavum</i> Y.Fukuyo 1981	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Subtropical Subsurface Water – Epipelagic Zone Okadaic acid, DTX1, Fast Acting Toxins
Harmful non-toxic	<i>Prorocentrum dentatum</i> F.Stein 1883	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Subtropical Subsurface Water – Epipelagic Zone
	<i>Prorocentrum micans</i> Ehrenberg 1834	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone
	<i>Triplos dens</i> (Ostenfeld & Johannes Schmidt) F.Gómez 2013	
	<i>Triplos furca</i> (Ehrenberg) F.Gómez 2013	
	<i>Triplos karstenii</i> (Pavillard) F.Gómez 2021	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Subtropical Subsurface Water – Epipelagic Zone
	<i>Triplos muelleri</i> Bory 1826	
	<i>Triplos fusus</i> (Ehrenberg) F.Gómez 2013	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Subtropical Subsurface Water – Epipelagic Zone
<i>Cerataulina pelagica</i> (Cleve) Hendeby 1937	Caribbean Surface Water - Epipelagic Zone Subtropical Subsurface Water – Epipelagic Zone Subtropical Subsurface Water – Mesopelagic Zone	

confirmed in Subtropical Subsurface Waters (SSW), characterized by average temperatures of 21 °C, a salinity of 36, and dissolved oxygen concentrations of around 3 mg·L⁻¹. Among the 15 compounds classified as toxic substances identified in the IOC-UNESCO list for the six species in question, the most prevalent were okadaic acid and the diarrhetic toxins (Table 2).

Non-toxic harmful species, such as *Prorocentrum dentatum*, *Triplos fusus*,

and *Cerataulina pelagica*, were also identified in the epipelagic zone of the SSW. The latter species was also observed in the mesopelagic zone of the SSW, at depths close to 250 m.

The CCOP is an industrial fishing zone of significant importance to the nation's economy and food security. The focus in this zone is on the capture of pelagic species, including *Coryphaena hippurus*, *Thunnus* spp., and *Makaira* spp. Therefore, the presence of these

HAB species highlights the need to implement a monitoring programme for marine toxins. Such a programme would help prevent potential public health problems and mitigate risks to the fishing and tourism industries.

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